

Data Management Plan

Title and identification number of the proposal	OTKA116228 Novel structural-functional aspects and genotype-phenotype correlations of the natural anticoagulants in thrombosis; focusing on antithrombin, protein C and protein S
Principal investigator / Host institution	Zsuzsanna Bereczky MD., PhD, University of Debrecen, Department of Laboratory Medicine
Scheduled starting date and conclusion of the project	15th of January, 2018
Are research data being produced during the course of the project?	Yes
Who is responsible for the management of research data? (Contact details, if not a member of the project team)	Zsuzsanna Bereczky MD., PhD University of Debrecen, Department of Laboratory Medicine
Please describe the type/nature of the data being produced during the course of the project.	Generate confocal microscopic images and used related patient data as well.
Please describe the procedure of the data collection.	Select the proper patient collection for further analysis purposes. This step needs a meta file, which contains all available relevant information about the selected patient. After that, the microscopic pictures were collected and stored in at least 3 different locations

	(microscopic PC, external hard drive, and OneDrive Cloud storage as well) to ensure the proper data storage.
Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored during the course of the project.	<p>The microscopic pictures were collected and stored in at least 3 different locations (microscopic PC, external hard drive, and Cloud as well) to ensure the data storage.</p> <p>The main requirement, is that all files are saved and archived in a software-dependent format during and after the course of the project. (In the given case, please use .csv for the excel sheet and .pdf format for word and ppt files)</p>
Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.	All relevant data is archived and uploaded to the cloud and saved on an external hard drive as well.
Please describe the accessibility of the research data.	The data will upload to the DEENK Dataverse, so all data will be available on the university repository.
Which research data of the project will be of open access?	The research data of the project will be restricted access.
Is there any reason or necessity to restrict the accessibility of the research data?	Based on the research agreement.
Do you use any standard metadata? (DublinCore, Datacite, etc.)	Yes, we used DublinCore.

Please describe where and how the metadata will be stored during the course of the project.

To ensure the proper data storage during the course of the project the metadata was stored in the abovementioned way, which was encrypted form on the local PC, external hard drive, and synchronized way to the OneDrive Cloud.

The last option is heavily important because the cloud storage ensures the version history, so we can easily track the changes as well during the course of the project.

Please describe how the metadata will be accessible?

The metadata will be accessible with restricted access on the DEENK Dataverse site.

Do you use standard or unique identifiers? (DOI, ORCID)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7481-6921>

Please describe where and how the metadata, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.

The metadata will be archived and uploaded to the cloud and saved on an external hard drive after the course of the project.

Does the handling of research data comply with the GDPR regulations?

Yes, of course. We have a general privacy policy related to the medical data procedure, which processing by the Clinical Center of the University of Debrecen regarding all medical activities performed concerning health conditions.